

Neutral Constituents of *Paederia foetida* Linn

V. J. TRIPATHI AND B. DASGUPTA

Department of Medicinal Chemistry, Institute of Medical Sciences, Varanasi-5

Manuscript received 25 January 1974; revised 5 July 1974; accepted 11 July 1974

PAEDERIA *foetida* Linn. (*Rubiaceae*: *Prasarani*) is a creeper grown from Central and East Himalayas, upto 5,000 ft., to Calcutta and Malay Peninsula. The whole plant is regarded as a specific for rheumatic affections in addition to various other uses described in the literature^f.

No other work except that the foetid smell of the plant is due to methyl mercaptan^g, has yet been reported. The present communication describes the isolation and characterisation of friedelin and β -sitosterol from the whole plant. Dry powder (450 g.) of *P. foetida* was extracted with petroleum ether (60°-80°) in a soxhlet extractor to yield 4.0 g. of crude extract. This extract, a mixture of at least four constituents as revealed by thin layer chromatography, was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina with elution of solvents in increasing order of polarity. Petroleum ether (60°-80°) eluate furnished friedelan-3-one (25 mg.), m. p. 260°-262° (EtOAc) (Lit^g. m. p. 263°-263.5°), R_f 0.35 (SiO_2 TIC, Pet. ether (60-80°): Benzene :: 1:1; Ac_2O : H_2SO_4 : EtOH, 5:5:90 as spraying reagent), $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ (M+426). Infrared spectrum of the compound shows bands at 1718 cm^{-1} (a six-membered carbonyl). The compound gave a D.N.P.H. derivative, m.p. 295°-296° (Benzene) (Lit^g. m.p. 297°-299°), R_f 0.78 (SiO_2 TIC, Pet. Ether (60°-80°): Benzene :: 1:1; self indicator). The mass spectrum of the parent ketone, in addition to the molecular ion peak at m/e 426 (100%) showed significant remnant ions at m/e 411 (M-Me, 33%), 341 (20%), 302 (80%),

273 (86%), 246 (70%), 232 (73%), 218 (80%), 205 (83%), suggesting its identity with friedelan-3-one.⁴

The benzene eluate afforded β -sitosterol (19 mg), m.p. 135°-136° (Acetone) (Lit.⁵ m.p. 140°), R_f 0.78 (SiO_2 TIC, CHCl_3 , L-B). It gave a pink to blue to green colour with Libermann-Burchard reagent. The mass spectrum of the sterol exhibited fragment ions at m/e 414 (M+, 100%), 399 (M-Me, 25%), 396 (M- H_2O , 30%), 381 [M ($\text{CH}_8 + \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 18%, 273 (M- $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{21}$, 50%), 271 (44%), 255 (m/e 273- H_2O , 60%), 231 (m/e 273- C_3H_8 , 30%) and 213 (m/e 231- H_2O , 50%), consistent with the fragmentation pattern which can be expected of β -sitosterol⁶.

References :

1. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, *Indian Medicinal Plants*, L. M. Basu, Allahabad, 2nd Edition, 1933 Vol. II, p. 1297.
2. P. K. Bose, Ajit Kumar Banerjee and Chandrachur, Ghosh, *Trans. Bose Research Inst.*, Calcutta, 1953-55, 8, 77.
3. J. Simonsen and W. C. J. Ross, "The Terpenes", Cambridge University Press, 1957, Vol. IV, p. 468.
4. H. Budzikiewicz, J. M. Wilson and Carl Djerassi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3688.
5. *Elsevier's Encyclopaedia of Organic Chemistry*, Elsevier Publishing Co., Inc., 1940, 145, 1808.
6. S. S. Friedland, G. H. Lane, R. T. Longman, K. E. Train, and M. J. O'Neal, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 31, 169; K. Biemann, *Mass spectrometry*, Mc Graw Hill Book Co., New York, 1962, p. 339.